

THE SITUATED EMOTION REGULATION QUESTIONNAIRE MANUAL

SERQ Version 1

Jason M. Harley^{a,b,c,d}, Keerat Grewal^a, Reinhard Pekrun^{e,f,g}, Jeffrey Wiseman^c, Susanne Lajoie^h, Allyson Hadwinⁱ, Ryan Brydges^j, Ning-Zi Sun^c, Gerald M. Fried^{a,c,d}, Sayed Azher^a, and Elene Khalil^k

^aDepartment of Surgery, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, H3A 0G4

^bResearch Institute of the McGill University Health Centre, Montreal, Canada, H3A 0G4

^cInstitute of Health Sciences Education, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, H3A 0G4

^dSteinberg Centre for Simulation and Interactive Learning (SCSIL), McGill University, Montreal, Canada, H3A 0G4

^eDepartment of Psychology, University of Essex, Colchester, U.K, CO4 3SQ

^fDepartment of Psychology & Pedagogy, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, Munich, Germany, D-80802

^gInstitute for Positive Psychology and Education, Australian Catholic University, Sydney, Australia, NSW 2059

^hDepartment of Educational and Counselling Psychology, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, H3A 0G4

ⁱDepartment of Educational Psychology & Leadership Studies, University of Victoria, Victoria, Canada, V8P 5C2

^jDepartment of Medicine, University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada, M5S 1A1

^kMcGill University Health Centre for Interprofessional Simulation, Montreal, Canada, H4A 3J1

Corresponding Author

Jason M. Harley, Department of Surgery, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, H3G 1A4; e-mail: jason.harley@mcgill.ca

Credit Author Statement

J.M.H., K.G., R.P., J.W., S.L., A.H., R.B., N.S.Z., G.M.F., S.A., and E.K. helped develop the items and structure of the self-report tool. J.M.H. and K.G. co-led development.

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1. Introduction

This manual presents insight into the development of the Situated Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (SERQ; section 2) as well as detailed justification for the discrete emotions chosen in the first part of this questionnaire (section 3). Section 4 is the pre-SERQ and section 5 is the post-SERQ. References are found in section 6.

The SERQ was developed on LimeSurvey which allows answers (e.g., drop down and open answer) responses to be carried forward to populate pre-existing fields in subsequent items. This helps bring context to subsequent items. This presents limitations, however, in this manual for illustrating the items.

Parts of this manual have also been published open access in Supplemental Material from Grewal, K., Azher, S., Moreno, M., Pekrun, R., Wiseman, J., Flake, J., Fried, G.M., Lajoie, S., Sun, N.Z., Khalil, E., & Harley, J.M. (2026). Medical trainees' emotions and their effects on perceptions of performance and team mood in team-based simulations. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 96, 306-336. DOI:10.1111/bjep.70017. Published CCBY.

2. Development of the SERQ.

To the authors' knowledge, there is no prior self-report tool that simultaneously captures emotional states, emotion regulation strategies, emotion regulation goals, perceptions of performance, and team mood (amongst other constructs) in medical education settings. Existing self-report tools, such as the Achievement Emotions Questionnaire (Pekrun et al., 2011, 2023) or the Ottawa Crisis Resource Management Global Rating Scale (Kim et al., 2006), are limited to collecting data on a few specific constructs (e.g., emotions or performance) in isolation. Researchers often require multiple tools to capture these constructs, which may be infeasible (e.g., due to time constraints) or impractical (e.g., due to survey fatigue) in applied research settings, such as simulation training (Colbert et al., 2021; Thibault et al., 2022).

The SERQ was envisioned to allow: (1) *researchers* to collect self-report data from health professional trainees on their concurrent emotional states before and after simulations, and their perceptions of performance, team mood, regulation strategies and more during simulations; (2) *educators* the ability to use this information to help guide debriefing content, especially during the emotional reactions phase; and (3) *trainees* the opportunity to reflect on their experiences before, during, and after simulations to potentially discuss during debriefings. Wording in the SERQ deliberately did not use jargon (e.g., emotion quadrants), and specialty (e.g., internal medicine) or profession-specific language (e.g., lead physician). While the SERQ was originally envisioned as a tool to enhance insight into health professional trainees' emotion regulation two non-health professional trainee versions have also been developed. One is currently in use with undergraduate students and another with astronauts. This manual focuses on the items developed for health professional trainees.

The SERQ includes a modified version of the Medical Emotion Scale (Duffy et al., 2020) drawing upon 9 items and adding 2 more items (stress and nervousness; see section 2 for more details). Additional items were adapted or inspired from Webster and Hadwin's Socio-Emotional

Sampling Tool (2014) and Socio-Emotional Reflection Tool (2012) to fit a health professions education context. This allowed participants to receive a self-narrative-style summary immediately after completing the SERQ that would capture their perceptions and possibly support further self-reflection. The adapted items were single-item responses which allowed for brevity to accommodate the logistical constraints of medical training. Four external medical experts provided feedback on the SERQ during its development.

Research collaborators with expertise in emotion, educational psychology, medicine, and medical education provided iterative feedback during meetings throughout the development of the SERQ. Initial meetings involved reviewing existing instruments and identifying appropriate tools and constructs to adapt for the SERQ. In subsequent sessions, collaborators were presented with draft versions of the SERQ items, engaged in structured group discussions, and provided detailed feedback on item inclusion, wording, relevance, and how to best preserve the theoretical and psychometric properties of the adapted items to support validity evidence based on *content* and *internal structure*. Collaborators also trialed the SERQ and offered feedback based on their user experience and expertise. The feedback from the research collaborators helped to ensure any modifications made to the SERQ were grounded in theoretical, empirical, or practical considerations.

Practical considerations for the SERQ included ensuring: 1) its brevity to prevent survey fatigue and fit within the logistical constraints of simulation training days, 2) survey items were understandable and relevant to participants, and 3) survey items were comprehensive enough to cover the expected range of responses and experiences. As an example, boredom was not included in the SERQ as it was not an emotion that would be expected within the crisis scenarios of the simulations. Emotion labels were selected to represent clusters of theoretically or practically similar emotions, such as happiness encompassing enjoyment (Lyubomirsky & Kurtz, 2009).

Prior to the use of the SERQ in the current study, informal semi-structured interviews were conducted with four medical experts external to the research team. These individuals reviewed the SERQ for clarity, relevance, feasibility, and comprehensiveness, and their feedback informed final revisions of the SERQ. As such, these interviews provided validity evidence based on *content* as enhancements to the relevance, representativeness, and clarity of the SERQ were made based on the feedback received.

3. Justification for Emotion Scale in the SERQ.

The SERQ was designed to capture participants' concurrent emotions before and after a simulation, as well as perceptions regarding performance and team mood. Using *The Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing* (American Educational Research Association et al., 2014) as the guiding framework for collecting validity evidence, we focused primarily on evidence based on *content*, *internal structure*, *response processes*, and *relations to other variables* for the SERQ. Evidence based on *content* refers to the relevance and representativeness of the underlying constructs of a measure to a given population of participants. Evidence based on *internal structure* refers to the items within a measure demonstrating relationships expected based upon conceptual frameworks. Evidence based on *response processes* pertains to the

cognitive processes that the participants engage in when using a measure, including how participants interpret and understand items within the measure. Evidence based on *relations to other variables* compares variables within a measure to either other variables within the measure or to external measures (i.e., external validity) to establish convergence or divergence for similar constructs.

Theoretical and previous empirical evidence was used to develop the SERQ to ensure it was relevant and representative for the participants, providing validity evidence based on *content*. Specifically, the SERQ's development was informed by theoretical models of achievement emotions (Harley et al., 2019; Harley & Pekrun, 2024; Pekrun, 2006, 2024), and drew from existing self-report instruments with evidence of validity, most notably the Medical Emotion Scale (MES; Duffy et al., 2020), which has demonstrated validity evidence with single-item emotional state measures in medical education contexts. Like the MES, we also collected data on concurrent emotional states from one moment in time, reducing recall effects as participants were not asked to recall their emotional states from the simulation. We selected emotions that spanned the four quadrants of emotions (positive activating, positive deactivating, negative activating, and negative deactivating) and were relevant to team-based simulation contexts. Curiosity and confusion were included as epistemic emotions relevant to learning and information processing (Vogl et al., 2020); shame, frustration, hopelessness, and nervousness as negative emotions likely to arise in high-pressure achievement situations (Pekrun & Stephens, 2010); pride, hopefulness, and happiness as positive achievement emotions linked to success and motivation (Frumos et al., 2024); and relief as a common response following the cessation of an unpleasant situation (Graham et al., 2023). Stress was also included given its practical relevance in medical education (Ahn et al., 2023; LeBlanc & Posner, 2022).

The same set of emotion items was used in both the pre- and post-SERQs to allow for consistency across timepoints and to reflect that all of the included emotions can be anticipatory and retrospective. For example, pride—which is typically retrospective—may be felt in anticipation of performing well before a simulation, shame may arise out of fear of poor upcoming performance, and hopelessness may reflect a lack of confidence about a future simulation. After a simulation, these emotions are likely to be retrospective: pride may be experienced as a reflection of a successful performance, shame may arise in response to a perceived mistake, and hopelessness may be experienced if the simulation that has concluded was perceived as overwhelming or unsuccessful. Using the same set of emotion items across both timepoints enabled consistent measurement across timepoints, recognizing that the object focus of each emotion may vary depending on individual appraisal and context.

As the SERQ was to be administered to medical trainees who may or may not have previous exposure to concepts of emotion or emotion regulation, it was imperative that the terminology used was easy to understand and interpretable by a general audience. Though stress is typically described as an affective state rather than an emotion (Gross, 2024), it is also used interchangeably with anxiety and nervousness, both colloquially and in the literature (Ahn et al., 2023; Gross, 2024; LeBlanc & Posner, 2022). Objective stress, referring to physiological responses (e.g., decreased heart rate variability), and subjective stress, referring to personal appraisals and perceived stress, can relate to various stressors, such as task difficulty (Joseph et al., 2022). As such, stress was included in the SERQ as well as nervousness to examine the

relationship between these states in the medical education context (analyses with stress and nervousness can be found in Grewal et al., 2025 Supplemental Materials VI-VIII, XVI-XVIII), though it was not formally analyzed in this study since we focused on emotions. The addition of nervousness and stress is consistent with other scales used to measure emotions in several studies, such as the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS; Watson et al., 1988) which includes “nervous” and the Socio-Emotional Sampling Tool (Bakhtiar et al., 2018) which includes “stressed”.

Given the need for brevity during simulation training, we opted for single-item emotion indicators, as used in the MES and other similar single-item scales with validity evidence, such as the Emotion-Value Questionnaire (Harley et al., 2015) and Epistemic Emotion Scale (Pekrun et al., 2017). Additionally, Gogol and colleagues (2014) found that single-item scales are viable to use when time is limited and are psychometrically sound compared to multi-item affective scales. The wording of SERQ emotion items closely mirrors the MES and items from other tools, such as the Achievement Emotions Questionnaire (Pekrun et al., 2011). Furthermore, previous work has provided evidence of validity based on *response processes* (i.e., evidence of how participants interpret and understand items) by demonstrating that the adjective rating scale is understood and interpreted similarly by individuals (e.g., Duffy et al., 2020; Fontaine et al., 2013; Shuman & Scherer, 2013).

Bivariate correlation strengths were defined according to Dancey and Reidy (2007). Correlations between emotions (Grewal et al., 2025 Supplemental Material VII-VIII) demonstrated that emotions sharing a common position in a valence and activation quadrant (e.g., negative activating emotions) typically exhibited moderate (defined as $.40 \leq r < .70$) to strong (defined as $.70 \leq r < 1.00$) positive correlations. Conversely, emotions that did not share positions in a common valence and activation quadrant exhibited negligible (defined as $.00 \leq r < .10$) to weak (defined as $.10 \leq r < .40$) positive correlations or were negatively correlated. These findings were consistent with theoretical (e.g., Pekrun, 2006, 2024) and empirical (e.g., Duffy et al., 2020) expectations, providing further evidence of validity based on *internal structure* and *content*.

4. Pre-Situated Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (SERQ)

We are interested in your thoughts and feelings both before and after your upcoming simulation, so please be honest with your answers.

Participation in this questionnaire will have no impact on your assignment of team leader in scenarios and no impact on any evaluations or assessments.

There are 11 questions in this survey.

Pre-SERQ

1. Please indicate how you feel **right now** about the **simulation** you are about to begin. *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

not at all very little moderately strongly very strongly

curious

confused

ashamed

relieved

stressed

frustrated

hopeless

happy

hopeful

not at all very little moderately strongly very strongly

proud

nervous

2. When I think about the simulation I am about to begin,

*I would most like to alter how _____ I feel. **

Please select an emotion you are currently experiencing (i.e., did not select "not at all" for in Question 1).

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- stressed
- nervous
- confused
- frustrated
- hopeless
- ashamed
- nothing
- something else _____

(if "something else" was selected) When I think about the simulation I am about to begin, I would most like to alter how _____ I feel.

I feel this _____

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- very strongly
- strongly
- moderately
- weakly
- very weakly

3. *I feel this way because _____*

4. *I think feeling this way is _____*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- very helpful
- helpful
- unhelpful

- detrimental
- very detrimental

5. *I would like to* _____

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- increase this emotion
- decrease this emotion
- switch this emotion to something else
- maintain this emotion
- do nothing about this emotion

6. I would like to _____ *by* _____

If you choose 'Other:' please also specify your choice in the accompanying text field.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- creating a good plan
- changing the plan or approach
- changing the goal(s) for the task
- visualizing success in the task
- remembering success in a similar task
- (re)focusing on the task
- changing the extent of focus on others' reactions
- accepting it and carrying on
- changing thoughts or beliefs
- reassessing how important the task is
- remembering the group's strengths
- taking deep breaths
- showing less emotion
- choosing to ignore it
- doing nothing
- Other _____

7. I would like to _____ *by* _____.

This is something _____

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I should do
- my other group members should do
- each of us should do independently
- we should all do together

Pre-SERQ Summary

What is the colour of your wristband(s)? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Red
- Blue
- Yellow
- Green
- Purple
- White
- Black
- Orange

Please provide your [**university**] email address below to receive a copy of your responses. *

Please use your [**university**] email address.

Thank you for completing the questionnaire. A copy of the summary below will be emailed to you:

When I think about the simulation I am about to begin, I would most like to alter how _____ I feel. I feel this _____. I feel this way because _____. I think feeling this way is _____. I would like to _____ by _____. This is something _____.

Thank you for completing this survey.

5. Post-Situated Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (SERQ)

We are interested in your thoughts and feelings both before and after the simulation you have just completed, so please be honest with your answers.

Participation in this questionnaire will have no impact on your assignment of team leader in scenarios and no impact on any evaluations or assessments.

There are 30 questions in this survey.

Post-SERQ

1. Please indicate how you feel **right now** about the **simulation** you have just completed.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

not at all very little moderately strongly very strongly

curious

confused

ashamed

relieved

stressed

frustrated

hopeless

happy

hopeful

not at all very little moderately strongly very strongly

proud

nervous

2. When I think about the simulation I have just completed, *the overall mood in my group was _____*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- very positive
- positive
- neutral
- negative
- very negative

3. *Overall, I am _____ satisfied with how I performed today.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- extremely
- very
- moderately
- not very
- not at all

4. *Overall, I am _____ satisfied with how my group performed today.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- extremely
- very
- moderately
- not very
- not at all

Think of a **challenging or negative** experience that occurred *during* the simulation.

5. *DURING this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- curious
- confused
- ashamed

- relieved
- stressed
- frustrated
- hopeless
- happy
- hopeful
- proud
- nervous
- something else _____

6. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly.

This feeling was _____

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- very strong
- strong
- moderate
- weak
- very weak

7. During this experience, I felt **ashamed** most dominantly. This feeling was **strong**.

When I felt this way, I _____

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- created a good plan
- changed the plan or approach
- changed the goal(s) for the task
- visualized success in the task
- remembered success in a similar task
- (re)focused on the task
- changed the extent of focus on others' reactions
- accepted it and carried on
- changed my thoughts or beliefs
- reassessed how important the task was
- took deep breaths
- remembered the group's strengths
- showed less emotion
- chose to ignore it
- did nothing
- Other _____

8. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, I _____.

- *Doing this* _____

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- increased my dominant emotion
- decreased my dominant emotion
- switched my dominant emotion to something else
- maintained my dominant emotion
- did not affect my dominant emotion at all

9. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, I _____.

- *Doing this* _____ *Therefore, doing this was* _____.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- very helpful
- helpful
- unhelpful
- detrimental
- very detrimental

10. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, I _____.

- *Doing this* _____ *Therefore, doing this was* _____.
- *Doing this made it* _____ *to complete the simulation.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- a lot harder
- a little harder
- neither harder nor easier
- a little easier
- a lot easier

11. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, I _____.

- *Doing this* _____ *Therefore, doing this was* _____.
- *Doing this made it* _____ *to complete the simulation.*
- *Next time, I should* _____.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- do the same thing
- do something different _____

12. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, I thought my group _____.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- created a good plan
- changed the plan or approach
- changed the goal(s) for the task
- visualized success in the task
- remembered success in a similar task
- (re)focused on the task
- changed the extent of focus on others' reactions
- accepted it and carried on
- changed thoughts or beliefs
- reassessed how important the task was
- took deep breaths
- remembered the group's strengths
- showed less emotion
- chose to ignore it
- did nothing
- Other _____

13. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, I thought my group _____.

This was something _____.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- my other group members did
- each of us did independently
- we all did together
- N/A (my group didn't do anything)

14. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, I thought my group _____.

- This was something _____.
- *Doing this* _____.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- increased my dominant emotion

- decreased my dominant emotion
- switched my dominant emotion to something else
- maintained my dominant emotion
- did not affect my dominant emotion at all

15. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.
When I felt this way, I thought my group _____.

- This was something _____.
- Doing this _____. *Therefore, doing this was _____.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- very helpful
- helpful
- unhelpful
- detrimental
- very detrimental

16. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.
When I felt this way, I thought my group _____.

- This was something _____.
- Doing this _____. *Therefore, doing this was _____.*
- *Doing this made it _____ to complete the simulation.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- a lot harder
- a little harder
- neither harder nor easier
- a little easier
- a lot easier

17. During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.
When I felt this way, I thought my group _____.

- This was something _____.
- Doing this _____. *Therefore, doing this was _____.*
- Doing this made it _____ to complete the simulation.
- *Next time, my group should _____.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- do the same thing
- do something different _____

Please provide your [university] email address below to receive a copy of your responses. *

Please write your answer here: _____

Please use your [university] email address.

Thank you for completing the questionnaire. A copy of the summary below will be emailed to you:

When I think about the simulation I have just completed, the overall atmosphere in my group was _____. Overall, I am _____ satisfied with how *I* performed today. Overall, I am _____ satisfied with how *my group* performed today.

I thought of a challenging or taxing experience that happened during the simulation.

During this experience, I felt _____ most dominantly. This feeling was _____.

When I felt this way, *I* _____.

- Doing this _____. Therefore, doing this was _____.
- Doing this made it _____ to complete the simulation.
- Next time, I should _____.

When I felt this way, I thought *my group* _____.

- This was something _____.
- Doing this _____. Therefore, doing this was _____.
- Doing this made it _____ to complete the simulation.
- Next time, my group should _____.

Thank you for completing this survey.

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